

**The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of
All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 1**

An Introduction to the Series of Manuscripts

Sumeet Shinde

ORCID: 0009-0000-5187-040X

Email: shinde.new.foundation@gmail.com

Date: 4-Jan 2026

Version: v1

Note : This is not the final version. I will publish final version separately, with or without modification. 'Version: final' would be mentioned on it

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20147555

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20147555>

Licence: © Sumeet Shinde 2026.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0) license. You are free to share and adapt this work, provided you give proper credit to the original author and distribute any derivative works under the same license.

Abstract

This manuscript is a part of a series of manuscripts named 'The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge'.

Being the first manuscript of the series, this manuscript is an introduction to this series of manuscripts. It includes my motivation & approach behind the explorations presented in this series, as well as for further explorations. It also includes an overview to what this series of manuscripts offers

Keywords

Introduction to series | Overview of series | My motivation & approach

List of series-manuscripts

Introduction to series

Manuscript 1

The New Foundation for All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 1

An introduction to the Series of manuscripts

Knowledge sub-series

Part 1 | Manuscript 2

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 2

The New Foundation of Knowledge Exploration: Part 1

Phenomenon of knowledge | Claim of knowledge

Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Knowledge 1

Part 2 | Manuscript 3

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 3

The New Foundation of Knowledge Exploration: Part 2

Journey towards knowledge | Core of indirect knowing | Mystery of knowing

Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Knowledge 2

Part 3 | Manuscript 4

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 4

The New Foundation of Knowledge Exploration: Part 3

Knowledge exploration process | Phenomenon of inherent similarity

Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Knowledge 3

Part 4 | Manuscript 5

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 5
The New Foundation of Knowledge Exploration: Part 4

Aid for knowledge exploration process
Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Knowledge 4

Part 5 | Manuscript 6

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 6
The New Foundation of Knowledge Exploration: Part 5

Aid for knowledge exploration process wrt perception phenomenon
Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Knowledge 5

Part 6 | Manuscript 7

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 7
The New Foundation of Knowledge Exploration: Part 6

Unanswered questions & unsolved paradoxes related to phenomenon of
knowledge & knowledge exploration
Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Knowledge 6

Mathematics sub-series

Part 1 | Manuscript 8

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 8
The New Foundation of Mathematics: Part 1

Core of phenomenon of mathematics | New mathematics system
Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Mathematics 1

Part 2 | Manuscript 9

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 9
The New Foundation of Mathematics: Part 2

Flaws related to current mathematics system
Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Mathematics 2

Part 3 | Manuscript 10

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 10
The New Foundation of Mathematics: Part 3

Unanswered questions & unsolved paradoxes & flaws in theorems related to
mathematics
Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Mathematics 3

Existence sub-series

Part 1 | Manuscript 11

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 11
The New Theory of Existence: Part 1

Reaching the real underlying mechanism of existence | This is eternity
Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Existence 1

Part 2 | Manuscript 12

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 12
The New Theory of Existence: Part 2

Philosophical theory of everything
Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Existence 2

Part 3 | Manuscript 13

The New and Axiom-Less Foundation of All Human Knowledge: Manuscript 13
The New Theory of Existence: Part 3

Theory of everything

Shortform to address this manuscript in content :: Existence 3

Introduction to the series

My motivation & approach

My motivation [related to explorations of content of this series]

This series of manuscripts is a product my devoted exploration of the purpose & the foundations of our existence.

I was focused on only one thing; and that thing was reaching the ultimate truth of this existence & our existence in it.

Even though based on this description it might seem that this exploration [explorations of this series] as being restricted to the domain of philosophy, but it is not. This exploration consists of the foundations of all the human knowledge.

And why is it so ?

Because, everything that exists is a part of the existence, we well as are a part of the ultimate truth.

And here is a thing, which we will also explored through the content of this series of manuscript. To know the ultimate truth of anything, you need to know the ultimate truth of everything.

So everything that exists, forms a part of the exploration of the ultimate truth of your existence.

My approach [related to explorations of content of this series]

During this exploration, my approach was not at all to follow the current ways of knowledge exploration Rather, I had more superior approach. And it was to keep my mindset completely open to adapt to any new possible ways. The focus was not on having new ways of exploration, but to have the way with highest possible potential for knowledge exploration.

And wrt my explorations, the only target I had was, taking my explorations to the deepest depth possible; no compromise on that & no satisfaction before that.

During the explorations, first I saturated myself with the current knowledge, with the focus on development of perception, and not mugging-up. There is a huge difference between both. Focusing on development of perception, rather than on mugging-up, allows you to consume knowledge with far greater potential & pace.

After I was saturated with the current knowledge, any further exploration based on current knowledge, was not getting my perception to be further developed, as well as the contradictions were very prominent & unresolvable based on current knowledge. So I took matters in my own hands, i.e. trying to push the present boundaries of perception, based on my own efforts.

Note

I desire to make my research open source, but my approach towards this explorations would always be to treat this exploration as first being my personal quest for knowledge exploration.

Overview of the series | [Advanced logic]

What is this series about ?

As the name suggests, this series of manuscripts provides the new and axiomless foundation for all human knowledge.

This foundation aligns the knowledge exploration, in the correct direction, and empowers it with the potential which would take the knowledge to the new depth, never possible before. This is the foundation which opens the doors for deeper knowledge.

What does this series addresses & offers ?

There are 3 aspects to this series, which makes this series of manuscripts a new foundation for all human knowledge. Following are those 3 aspects

1. It offers the new axiom-less foundation of knowledge & knowledge exploration
2. It offers the bottom-up approach of knowledge exploration, which is completely missing in current foundation
3. It offers the explorations of bottom-up approach, already done to a major extent

The most core fundamental aspect which this series addresses is, the lack of depth of understanding in the current foundation of all knowledge; which has lead the axioms to exist in the very foundation of current knowledge. And this is the most core flaw in current knowledge foundation & current knowledge exploration.

Here is a thing which we would explore through this series. Advanced logic with non-advanced witness of existence [i.e. without advanced scientific experiments], has far greater potential for deeper & correct knowledge, than compared to the advanced witness of existence [witness of advanced scientific experiments] with non-advanced logic. And the thing here is that, the advanced witness done later, has to be & is, in alignment with the deeper depths explored through advanced logic & non-advanced witness. This is about bottom-up approach of knowledge exploration [which is completely missing in current knowledge & knowledge exploration].

This series addresses the issue of non-advanced logic in the current foundation; buy giving the advanced logic. This advancement of logic is far advancement than the current logic which the current foundation of knowledge is based on.

The major aspect of the new foundation is, the advanced logic & the bottom-up approach of knowledge exploration that it offers, which is completely missing in current knowledge & knowledge exploration. And this major aspect opens the doors for new science, the new knowledge. It shows the correct knowledge gap through bottom-up approach, as well as does the explorations of the bottom-up approach, to a major extent.

With this, it offers not just the new axiom-less foundation, but also the new knowledge itself.

'The core idea' of axiom-less foundation, an advanced logic

Bottom-up approach of knowledge exploration

The core idea of the axiom-less foundation of all human knowledge is that, it is limitations that is our guide towards knowledge. But what we witness in material world is possibilities [possibilities manifested out of all the possibilities], not limitations. Limitations are explored through analysis. Knowledge of limitations is an analysis.

And limitations can be explored, only from the depth of absolute limitations. In other words, to explore limitations, first we need to explore absolute limitations. And then we explore all the non-absolute limitations, from the depth of absolute limitations.

And this the bottom-up approach of knowledge exploration.

Top-down approach vs bottom-up approach

Bottom-up approach of knowledge is our guide, our compass towards knowledge.

Without which, i.e. based on mere top-down approach, we cannot explore knowledge in right direction; rather we cannot even know the right direction of exploration. In other words, only bottom-up approach of knowledge gives us the correct knowledge gap to be filled.

Trying to fill the knowledge gap based on mere top-down approach, is wrong direction of knowledge exploration, i.e. a pseudo science.

Knowledge exploration based on top-down approach needs axioms, i.e. assumptions related to absolute limitations.

Knowledge exploration based on bottom-up approach is axiom-less, as it is based not on assumptions, but on depth of understanding, which is based on the witness of absolute limitations.

Start of bottom-up approach

And the exploration of absolute limitations starts at exploration of the absolute limitations of the phenomenon of knowledge. In other words, the bottom-up approach of knowledge exploration, starts at the witness of the absolute limitations of the phenomenon of knowledge itself.

This is because the most core of our knowledge is, the phenomenon of knowledge itself. And the absolute limitations of phenomenon of knowledge are an inevitable core of all our knowledge.

And the base of phenomenon of knowledge is perception. Core of all our knowledge is perception. Rather, it is perception which we classify as knowledge, belief, faith & superstition. So absolute limitations of perception are inevitable in knowledge exploration. Rather exploration of absolute limitations of existence, start with absolute limitations of perception.

The alignment of absolute limitations of our perception and absolute limitations of existence, is based on the fact that we are also a part of existence. The absolute limitations of perception, has to be & are in alignment with the absolute limitations of existence.

The absolute limitations of perception are as follows

1. Phenomenon of inherent similarity
2. Thinking framework [limitation of phenomenon of thinking]

Further in series

We will explore all this in manuscripts of 'Knowledge sub-series'
I just mentioned it here so as to keep the track of the context of this series, clear from the beginning.

Synopsis of what this series offers

Following is the synopsis of what this series of manuscripts offers

- Depth of understanding of the phenomenon of knowledge
- Foundations of knowledge exploration related
 - Offers a foundation of knowledge exploration
- Foundations of knowledge exploration system related
 - Offers a new foundation of knowledge exploration systems
 - Including the mathematics system, language system, etc
 - Offers new mathematics system [including a new phenomenon which is inevitable & critical for exploration of the dynamic of material world]

- Addresses the flaws in the current foundations of knowledge exploration system
- Offers the correct knowledge gap to be explored in knowledge exploration; hence offers the new knowledge
- Explorations based on correct knowledge gap related
 - Shows the real underlying mechanism of existence; unknown ever before
 - Offers the philosophical theory of everything
 - Offers the theory of everything; based on a new theory of existence
 - Dissolves the boundary between science & philosophy
 - Offers an absolute evidence for GOD [eternal oneness | the ultimate form]
 - Offers new theory of evolution
- Related to current foundations
 - Various major unanswered questions are answered
 - Various major paradoxes are solved

This manuscript is a complete new foundation for all knowledge & knowledge-exploration, based on multiple logic-breakthroughs.

Note

The hardness of a material is known, only when you try to break it. Same way, the firmness [flawlessness] of this foundation, can be known only when the efforts are made to break its firmness, i.e. to find the flaws in it.

The foundation is flawless which includes all the knowing related to the existence.